

The spider wasp family Pompilidae (Hymenoptera: Aculeata: Pompiloidea) in Uzbekistan: annotated checklist with first faunal records

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Abstract

This paper presents, for the first time, a review of the fauna of spider wasps (Pompilidae) of Uzbekistan. The review includes 132 species and 1 subspecies, 4 species undetermined to species level (sp.), belonging to 28 genera, 8 tribes, and 3 subfamilies recorded within the territory of Uzbekistan. The data are based on published literature and materials collected during 1909–1978, which are preserved in the Entomological Collection of the State Museum of Nature of Uzbekistan. Among these, 9 species are recorded for the first time for the fauna of Uzbekistan, namely: *Cryptocheilus (Cryptocheilus) alternatus caspius* Gussakovskij, 1952; *Priocnemis (Priocnemis) minuta* (Vander Linden, 1827); *Priocnemis (Umbripennis) gypsochtona* Gussakovskij, 1930; *Tachyagetes (Tachyagetes) excellens* (Haupt, 1930); *Arachnospila (Ammosphex) trivialis* (Dahlbom, 1843); *Arachnospila (Arachnospila) binaeva* Haupt, 1930; *Arachnospila (Arachnospila) rufa* (Haupt, 1927); *Paracyphononyx pavlovskyi* Gussakovskij, 1952; *Arachnotheutes rufithorax* (Costa, 1882).

Keywords

New record, aculeate wasps, fauna, Central Asia

Introduction

The family Pompilidae (commonly known as spider wasps) is one of the largest families among the aculeate wasps. The world fauna of this family comprises 254 genera and 4,855 species, of which approximately 65 genera and about 1,000 species occur in the Palaearctic region (Loktionov and Lelej 2017); In the Neotropical region, there are 63 genera and 946 species (Fernández et al. 2022). Spider wasps are especially abundant in tropical regions. In North America, 35 genera have been recorded; in Australia, more than 40 genera (Elliott 2007); and in Mexico, 46 genera and 305 species, including 126 endemic species (Vanoye-Eligio et al. 2021). Within the territory of the former Soviet Union, about 285 species have been recorded, with the highest diversity in Transcaucasia and Central Asia (Loktionov and Lelej 2014).

The family Pompilidae (spider wasps) includes five subfamilies: Ctenocerinae, Notocyphinae, Ceropalinae, Pepsinae, and Pompilinae (Waichert et al. 2015), of which the last three have been recorded in Uzbekistan.

Spider wasps (Pompilidae) lead a solitary lifestyle, yet they are morphologically and biologically diverse. They nest in the ground, construct mud nests, or utilize cavities in wood or plant stems. Most species hunt spiders themselves, while others use spiders captured by wasps of the subfamily Ceropalinae, or lay their eggs in the nests of other pompilids (on the spider). Thus, they can be classified as predators, ectoparasitoids, and kleptoparasites.

The study of the Hymenoptera fauna in Central Asia has a history of almost 150 years. A significant contribution to the research on spider wasps in Central Asia during the XIX century was made by F. Morawitz (1891), O.I. Radoszkowski (1877a, 1877b, 1887, 1888), V.V. Gussakovskij (1926, 1929, 1930, 1931, 1932, 1933, 1935, and others). Later, in the 20th century, important studies were conducted by A.S. Lelej, V.M. Loktionov, M.V. Mokrousov, L. Móczar, H. Wolf, S.L. Zonstein, and other researchers.

The fauna of spider wasps in Central Asia is rich, yet it remains insufficiently studied in many regions, particularly in Uzbekistan. Comprehensive faunistic research on the Pompilidae of Uzbekistan is practically absent. In the literature, there are only scattered reports on the occurrence of spider wasps within the territory of Uzbekistan (Tobias 1978; Insects of Uzbekistan 1993; Lelej 2000, 2005; Wahis and Schmid-Egger 2002; Loktionov and Lelej 2009, 2012, 2014, 2017; Loktionov 2011; Lelej and Loktionov 2012, 2017; Shlyakhtenok 2013; Shlyakhtenok et al. 2017, 2021), as well as notes on sporadic collections from specific regions of the republic (Gussakovskij, 1933; Davletshina et al. 1979; Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007; Lelej et al. 2017), or descriptions of new species (Radoszkowsky 1877b; Móczár 1978a, 1978b, 1986, 1987, 1989; Wolf 1982, 1987,

1988a, 1988b, 1990, 1994, 1998, 2001, 2004, 2005; Zonstein 2000, 2001a, 2001b, 2001c, 2002a, 2002b, 2007a, 2007b, etc.; Wahis and Schmid-Egger 2002; Zonstein, Zonstein 2007; Mokrousov and Zryanin 2015; Zonstein, Wahis 2015).

The aim of this study is to compile an annotated list of road wasps (Hymenoptera: Aculeata: Pompiloidea) of the fauna of Uzbekistan, based on literature sources and specimens from the Entomological Collection of the State Museum of Nature of Uzbekistan.

Materials and methods

The study was based on over 300 specimens of spider wasps collected between 1909 and 1978 across the territory of Uzbekistan, preserved in the Entomological Collection of the State Museum of Nature of Uzbekistan (SMNUz). In addition, the research utilized literature sources, including the latest catalogues (Lelej and Loktionov 2012; Shlyakhtenok 2013; Loktionov and Lelej 2017) and other references concerning Pompilidae species recorded in Uzbekistan.

Abbreviations

GMPUz – State Museum of Nature of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

IZ AS RUz – Institute of Zoology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

TAUI – Zoological Museum, Tel Aviv University, Tel Aviv, Israel.

ZISP – Zoological Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences, St. Petersburg, Russia.

ZMMU – Zoological Museum of Moscow University, Moscow, Russia.

Results

Based on the analysis of literature sources on spider wasps and the materials from the Entomological Collection of the State Museum of Nature of Uzbekistan, an annotated list of spider wasps of Uzbekistan was compiled. The list below includes references to literature sources, specimen data, and collection localities of the pompilid species.

The superfamilies, families, tribes and genera are arranged according to their taxonomic classification, and the species within each genus are listed in alphabetical order.

Class: Insecta (Linnaeus, 1758) - Insects

Subclass: Pterygota Gegenbaur, 1878 – Winged or higher insects

Order: Hymenoptera Linnaeus, 1758 - Hymenopterans

Suborder: Apocrita Gerstaecker, 1867 – Narrow-waisted wasps

Superfamily: Pompiloidea

Family POMPILIDAE Fabricius, 1798 - Spider Wasps

Subfamily CEROPALINAE Radoszkowski, 1888

Genus *Ceropales* Latreille, 1796

Subgenus *Bifidoceropales* Priesner, 1969

Ceropales (*Bifidoceropales*) *pygmaea pygmaea* Kohl, 1880 (Guzar: see Móczár 1978b: 350).

Subgenus *Ceropales* Latreille, 1796

Ceropales (*Ceropales*) *albicincta seraxensis* Radoszkowski, 1893 (Khiva, etc.: see Móczár 1978a: 134).

Ceropales (*Ceropales*) *bogdanovii bogdanovii* Radoszkowski, 1877 (Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 160).

Ceropales (*Ceropales*) *bogdanovii sabulosa* F. Morawitz, 1891 (Uzbekistan: see Móczár 1978b: 358; Loktionov and Lelej, 2017: 160).

Ceropales (*Ceropales*) *helvetica helvetica* Tournier, 1889 (Uzbekistan: see Móczár 1989: 28; Loktionov and Lelej, 2017: 160).

Ceropales (*Ceropales*) *maculata* (Fabricius, 1775) (Fergana Valley: see Radoszkowski 1877b: 14).

Material: Namangan Region: “Podsha Ata, 15.VIII.33”, det. “*Ceropales maculata nigra* Rad., ♀” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Ceropalus (*Ceropales*) *opator* Priesner, 1955 (Tashkent: see Wolf 1998: 338).

Ceropales (*Ceropales*) *solskii* Radoszkowski, 1877 (Uzbekistan: see Gussakovskij 1926: 251; Móczár 1987: 140).

Ceropales (*Ceropales*) *variegata* (Fabricius, 1798) (Samarqand Region: see Moczár 1978a: 117).

Subgenus *Hemiceropales* Priesner, 1969

Ceropales (Hemiceropales) cribrata cribrata Costa, 1881 (Uzbekistan: see Móczár 1986: 332; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 161).

Subfamily PEPSINAE Lepeletier de Saint-Fargeau, 1845**Tribe Auplopodini Pate, 1946 (1934)****Subtribe Auplopodina Pate, 1941****Genus *Auplopus* Spinola, 1841****Subgenus *Auplopus* Spinola, 1841**

Auplopus (Auplopus) rectus (Haupt, 1927) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 336; Loktionov and Lelej, 2017: 165).

Auplopus (Auplopus) rufiventris (Radoszkowski, 1877) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 337; Tashkent Region: see Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002: 116; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: Jizzakh Region: “Uzbekistan, Turkestanskii hr., Zaaminskii zap, Kulsai, 2100 m, 7.08.1961, Bekuzin”, det. “S. Zonstein, 1996 – *Auplopus rufiventris* (Radosz., 1877)” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Tribe Pepsini Lepeletier, 1845**Genus *Cryptocheilus* Panzer, 1806****Subgenus *Adonta* Billberg, 1820**

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) albosignatus Šustera, 1924 (Pungan, Samarqand: see Wolf 1998: 338).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) bequaerti Šustera, 1924 (Pungan: see Wolf 1998: 338).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) carinatus Zonstein, 2001 (Zeravshan Mts.: see Zonstein 2001c: 136).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) confinis Haupt, 1927 (Jizzax: see Wolf 1998: 338).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) desertorum (Morawitz, 1891) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 338; Tashkent Region: see Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002: 116; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) fischeri (Spinola, 1838) (Uzbekistan: see Zonstein 2007b: 226; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 161).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) guttulatus (Costa, 1887) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 339; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 161).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) hispanicus Šusterka, 1924 (Samarqand: see Wolf 1998: 339).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) moravitzi (Radoszkowski, 1877) (Samarkand Region: see Zonstein 2007b: 229).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: “Ferganskaya dolina, st. Iessen, ady`ry`, 19.V.1940, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Cryptocheilus* aff. *moravitri*, ♀” – 1♀; vy`gorela, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Cryptocheilus* aff. *moravitri*, ♂” – 1♂ (GMPUz).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) nigripennis (Gussakovskij, 1952) (Surkhandarya Region: see Zonstein 2007b: 229-230).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) nigrifulus Gussakovskij, 1952 (Samarqand, etc.: see Wolf 1998: 339).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) notatus notatus (Rossi, 1792) (Zeravshan Rg.: see Wolf 2004: 1146; Uzbekistan: Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 161).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: Tashkent Region: “Ugamskii hr., usch. Kainarsay, 15.07.1977, G.F. Kolyuh”, det. “S. Zonstein, 1996 – *Cryptocheilus* sp. ex. gr. *notatus*” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) octomaculatus (Rossi, 1790) (Tashkent Region: see Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002: 116; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) oxianus Zonstein, 2001 (Surkhandarya Region: see Zonstein 2001c: 135-136).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) richardsi Móczár, 1953 (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 339; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 161).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: Tashkent Region: “Karzhantau, lyucerna I p., koshenie, 21.VII.37”, det. “*Cryptocheilus variegatus* F.”; “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Cryptocheilus richardsi* Mocz.” – 1♀; “Ferganskaya dolina, st. Iessen, na gigantskom molochoe, 19.V.1940, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Cryptocheilus richardsi* Mocz.” – 3♀, 2♂; “Ferganskaya dolina, k. Yaz-Yavan, solodka, 12.V.1940, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Cryptocheilus richardsi* Mocz., ♀” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) rogenhoferi (Radoszkowski, 1887) (Tashkent Region: see Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002: 116; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170; Tashkent, Kashkadarya, Bukhara Regions: Zonstein 2007b: 235).

Material: “UZBEKISTAN: Tashkent Region: “Boshkizy`l saj, trav. kust, 17.VII.51, P. Banov”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Cryptocheilus rogenhoferi* Rad., ♀” – 1♀; “Kara-Mazar, 10.VI.29, I. Yank[ovskij]”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Cryptocheilus rogenhoferi* Rad., ♀” – 1♀; “Ferganskaya dolina, st. Iessen, na gigantskom molochae, 19.V.1940, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Cryptocheilus rogenhoferi* Rad., ♂” – 1♂ (GMPUz).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) sarafschani (Radoszkowski, 1877) (Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya Regions: see Zonstein 2007b: 239).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) sarbaz S. Zonstein, 2007 (Tashkent: see Zonstein 2007b: 241).

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) semicastaneus (F. Morawitz, 1894) (Samarqand: see Wolf 1998: 339)

Cryptocheilus (Adonta) variabilis (Rossi, 1790) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 339; 2005: 1746; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 161).

Subgenus *Chyphonocheilus* Wolf, 1970

Cryptocheilus (Chyphonocheilus) rubellus (Eversmann, 1846) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 339; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 162).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: “Golodnaya step`”, det. “*Cryptocheilus rubellus* Ev., ♀” – 1♀, “Chr. Kos. Aral S.-D., 3.VI.11, D. Lyutin”; det. “*Cryptocheilus rubellus* Ev., ♀” – 1♀; 19.., det. “*Cryptocheilus rubellus* Ev., ♀” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Subgenus *Cryptocheilus* Panzer, 1806

Cryptocheilus (Cryptocheilus) alternatus caspius Gussakovskij, 1952

Material: First record for UZBEKISTAN: “pusty`nya Yu. Kizil Kum, k. sot. Nurat.[inskij] xr., 22.V.26, E`ksp.”, det. “*Cryptochilus annulatus caspius* Giss., ♀” – 2♀, (GMPUz).

Cryptocheilus (Cryptocheilus) discolor (Fabricius, 1793) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 338; 2005: 1746; Tashkent Region: see Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002: 116; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170; Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya: see Mokrousov and Zryanin 2015: 39; Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 162).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: Jizzakh Region: “xr. Nuratau, okr. s. Farish, 24.05.1972, G.F. Kolyux”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Cryptocheilus discolor* (F., 1973), ♀” – 1♀; Tashkent Region: “Ok-tash, 25.V.26, N. Kuznecov”, det. “*Cryptochilus discolor* F., ♀” – 2♀; “r. Sy`r-Dar`ya, Chittatugaj, 1.07.1961, G.F. Kolyux”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 *Cryptocheilus discolor* (F., 1973), ♀” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Genus *Hemipepsis* Dahlbom, 1844

Hemipepsis sogdiana Zonstein, 2000 (Tashkent Region: see Zonstein 2000: 167-168; Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002: 116; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170).

Tribe Priocnemini Banks, 1934

Genus *Claveliocnemis* Wolf, 1968

Claveliocnemis brachypteris (Gussakovskij, 1935) (= *Priocnemis brachypteris* Gussakovskij, 1935) (Samarkand, Surkhandarya Regions: see Zonstein 2007a: 209-210).

Claveliocnemis incisipennis Wolf, 1968 (Samarkand, Surkhandarya Regions: see Zonstein 2007a: 210-211).

Genus *Priocnemis* Schiødte, 1837

Subgenus *Priocnemis* Schiødte, 1837

Priocnemis (Priocnemis) agilis (Shuckard, 1837) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 344; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 163; Shlyakhtenok et al. 2017: 30).

Priocnemis (Priocnemis) exaltata (Fabricius, 1775) (Uzbekistan: see Shlyakhtenok et al. 2017: 30).

Priocnemis (Priocnemis) hyalinata (Fabricius, 1793) (= *Priocnemis (Priocnemis) femoralis* (Dahlbom, 1829)) (Uzbekistan: see Tobias 1978: 100; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 163; Shlyakhtenok et al. 2017: 30).

Priocnemis (Priocnemis) minuta (Vander Linden, 1827).

Material: First record for UZBEKISTAN: “Xivinskij oasis, p. Dashak, 24.IV.1941, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Priocnemis minuta* V.D.L., ♂” – 1♂ (GMPUz).

Priocnemis (Priocnemis) parvula Dahlbom, 1845 (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 345; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 163; Shlyakhtenok et al. 2017: 30, 34).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: Tashkent Region: “Karzhantau, galechnik, 25.VII.1939, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Priocnemis* off. *parvula* V.L., ♀” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Subgenus *Umbripennis* Junco y Reyes, 1947

Priocnemis (Umbripennis) fallax Verhoeff, 1892 (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 2005: 1750; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 163).

Priocnemis (Umbripennis) gypsochtona Gussakovskij, 1930.

Material: First record for UZBEKISTAN: “Podsha Ata, 15.VIII.33, I.Ya.[nkovskij]”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Priocnemis (Umbripennis) gypsochtona* Guss., ♀, ♂ – 1♀, 1♂ (GMPUz).

Priocnemis (Umbripennis) hankoi Móczár, 1944 (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 344; Wolf 2005: 1750; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 163; Shlyakhtenok et al. 2017: 34).

Priocnemis (Umbripennis) melanosoma Kohl, 1880 (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 345).

Priocnemis (Umbripennis) perturbator (Harris, 1780) (Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 164; Shlyakhtenok et al. 2017: 37).

Priocnemis (Umbripennis) sulci Balthazar, 1943 (Yangikishloq: see Wolf 1998: 344).

Priocnemis (Umbripennis) vulgaris (Dufour, 1841) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 345; Wolf 2005: 1750; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 164).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: Tashkent Region: “Ok-tash, 25.V.25, M. Kuznecov», det. “*Priocnemis mimulus* Wesm., ♀”; “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Priocnemis (Umbripennis) vulgaris* Duf., ♀” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, verx. Axit. v vozga?, 6.VII.37”, det. “*Priocnemis mimulus* Wesm.”; “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Priocnemis (Umbripennis) vulgaris* Duf., ♀” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, zont. lugostep`, czvety` F. karatavica, 31.V.1940, Obuxova”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Priocnemis (Umbripennis) vulgaris* Duf., ♀” – 16♀, “Karzhantau, myatlikovaya step`, 22.VI.1940, Obuxova”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Priocnemis (Umbripennis) vulgaris* Duf., ♀” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, trava u rusla, 30.VI.1940, Obuxova”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Priocnemis (Umbripennis) vulgaris* Duf., ♀” – 1♀; “Turanskij xr., okr. Ky`zy`l-Mazara. ushh. Yandarsajb, 8.08.1976, G.F. Kolyux”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Priocnemis vulgaris* (Dufour)” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Subfamily POMPILINAE Latreille, 1805**Tribe Anopliini Ashmead, 1902****Genus *Anoplius* Dufour, 1834****Subgenus *Anoplius* Dufour, 1834**

Anoplius (Anoplius) aberrans Gussakovskij, 1932 (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 332; Lelej and Loktionov 2012: 411; Loktionov and Lelej 2012b, 2014, 2017: 172).

Anoplius (Anoplius) concinnus (Dahlbom, 1843) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 333, 2005: 1742; Tashkent Region: see Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170; Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 172).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: “Tashkent, 27.VI.1919, Kviton”, det. “*Anoplius concinnus* Dhlb., ♀” – 1♀; Tashkent Region: “Uzbekistan, xr. Karzhantau, Taldy’saj, 7.07.1956, A.A. Bekuzin”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Anoplius* (s. str.) *concinnus* Dhlb.” – 1♀; “Uzbekistan, xr. Karzhantau, Terekbulak, 2.08.1956, A.A. Bekuzin”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Anoplius* (s. str.) *concinnus* Dhlb.” – 1♀; “Uzbekistan, xr. Karzhantau, Xumsan, 14-16.07.1958, A.A. Bekuzin”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Anoplius* (s. str.) *concinnus* Dhlb.” – 5♀; “Fergansk. dol., k. Yaman-aul, peski, 17.V.1940, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Anoplius* (s. str.) *concinnus* Dhlb., ♂” – 1♂; “Uzb. SSR, Fergansk. dol., st. Iessen, na gigantskom molochae, 19.05.1940, Anonym leg.”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Anoplius concinnus* Dhlb.” – 1♀; “Uzbekistan, Fergansk. dol., Tyura-Kurganskij r-n, na molochae *Euphorbia* sp., 19.05.1940, Anonym leg.”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Anoplius concinnus* Dhlb.” – 4♀; “Uzbekistan, okrestnosti Andizhana, 15.05.1957, Coll. Avanesova”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Anoplius* (s. str.) *concinnus* Dhlb.” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Anoplius (Anoplius) nigerrimus (Scopoli, 1763) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 333; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 172).

Anoplius (Anoplius) separatus (Haupt, 1929) (Uzbekistan: see Lelej 2005: 132).

Subgenus *Arachnoproctonus* Howard, 1901

Anoplius (Arachnoproctonus) infuscatus (Vander Linden, 1827) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 333; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 172).

Material: “UZBEKISTAN, dol. r. Sy`r-Dar`ya, Chattatuchaj, 2.06.1961, G.F. Kolyux”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Anoplius* sp. aff. *infuscatus* (V.D.L.)” – 1♀; Tashkent Region: “xr. Karzhantau, trava u rusla, pritok Ugama, 6.VI.1940, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Anoplius* sp. aff. *infuscatus*” – 1♀; Ferghana Valley: “Fergansk. dol., Yaz-Yavan saj, 7.V.1940, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Anoplius* sp. aff. *infuscatus*” – 4♀; “Fergansk. dol., k. Ming-Bulak, 13.V.1940, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Anoplius* sp. aff. *infuscatus*” – 1♀; “Fergansk. dol., k. Ming-Bulak, boloto, 14.V.1940, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Anoplius* sp. aff. *infuscatus*” – 1♀; “Fergansk. dol., st. Iessen, na gigantskom molochae, 19.V.1940, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Anoplius* sp. aff. *infuscatus*” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Anoplius (Arachnoproctonus) pseudinfuscatus Wolf, 1997 (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 333).

Anoplius (Arachnophroctonus) schlettereri (Radoszkowski, 1888) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 333; 2005: 1743; Tashkent Region: see Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002: 116; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: “Xivinskij oazis, peski dol. Kori, 28.IV.1941, Chirkun” – 1♀; “Xorezmsk. obl., k. Gazavat, peski, 13.V.41, Chirkun” – 1♀; Tashkent Region: “Yu.-Z. T.-Sh., Chet. saj, 5.VI.29, I. Yank.”[ovskij], ”N. Meyer det. – *Anoplius schlettereri* Rad.” – 1♀; “Ak-tash, 25.V.26, N. Kuznecov”, det. – “*Anoplius schlettereri* Rad., ♀” – 5♀; “Karzhantau, subal`p. lug, 1.VIII.37”, leg. Obuxova, det. “*Anoplius schlettereri* Red.” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, zalezhi, Toloka, 6.IV.1940, Obuxova” – 1♀; Ferghana Valley: “Fergansk. dol., st. Iessen, ady`ry`, 19.V.1940, Chirkun”, “N. Meyer det. – *Anoplius schlettereri* Rad.” – 2♀; “Fergansk. dol., st. Iessen, na gigantskom molochae, 20.V.1940, Chirkun”, “N. Meyer det. – *Anoplius schlettereri* Rad.” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Anoplius (Arachnophroctonus) viaticus (Linnaeus, 1758) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 334; 2005: 1743; Navoi, Kashksdarya Regions: see Mokrousov and Zryanin 2015: 39; Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 172).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: Khorezm Region: “Xivinsk. oazis, peski oz. Kari, 28.IV.41, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Anoplius viaticus* (L., 1758), ♀” – 1♀; “Xorezmsk. obl., zakreplen. peski, k. Dashak, 26.IV.41, Chirkun” – 1♀, Jizzakh Region: “xr. Nuratau, Uzbekistan, okr. s. Farish, 19.04.1976, G.F. Kolyux”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Anoplius viaticus* (Linnaeus, 1758)” – 2♀; “Tashkent, lyucerna, 31.III.1941, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Anoplius viaticus* (L., 1758), ♀” – 2♀; “Tashkent, Kara-Kamy`sh, 15.IV.1942, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Anoplius viaticus* (L., 1758), ♀” – 1♀; Tashkent Region: “Karzhantau, subal`pijskij lug, uch. Singach, 28.VII.1938, Obuxova”, det. “*Anoplius viaticus* L., ♀” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, ovrag, 12.V.39, Obuxova” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, subal`pijskij lug, oz. Susingan, 26.VI.1939, Obuxova”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Anoplius viaticus* (L., 1758), ♀” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, zalezhi, Xumsan, 27.VI.1939, Obuxova”, “N. Meyer det. – *Anoplius viaticus* L., ♀” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, subal`pijskij lug, 3.VII.1939, Obuxova”, det. “*Anoplius viaticus* L., ♀” – 2♀; “Karakuzsaj, 29.VI.1939, Xolm”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Anoplius viaticus* L.” – 3♀; “Karzhantau, subal`pijskij lug, Karakuzsaj, 3.VII.1939, Obuxova”, “N. Meyer det. – *Anoplius viaticus* L., ♀” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, subal`pijskij lug, Vost. Ming-Bulaka, 8.VII.1939, Obuxova”, det. “*Anoplius viaticus* L., ♀” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, zalezhi, Toloka, 6.IV.1940, Obuxova” – 13♀; “Karzhantau, zont. lugostep`, 28.IV.1940, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Anoplius viaticus* L., ♀” – 3♀; “Karzhantau, Tipchak, step`, 21.V.1940, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Anoplius viaticus* L., ♀” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, kserof. kamen. step`, 27.V.1940, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Anoplius viaticus* L., ♀” – 3♀; “Karzhantau, zont. lugostep`, czv. F. karatavica, 31.V.1940, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Anoplius viaticus* L., ♀” – 4♀; “Karzhantau, Savansaj, 22.06.1966, G.F. Kolyux”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Anoplius viaticus* (Linnaeus, 1758)” – 1♀; “Ak-tash, 25.V.1926, N. Kuznecov”, det. “*Anoplius viaticus* L., ♀” – 1♀; “st. Sary`-Agach, 24.VII.1934, K. Skopin, det. – *Ano-*

plius viaticus L., ♀” – 1♀; “p. zapovedn. Bash-kzy`l saj, raznotrav. step`, 4.VII.1951”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Anoplius viaticus* L.” – 1♀; “Gandzha, na molochae, 6.V.1933, det. Gussakovskij – *Anoplius viaticus* L., ♀” – 1♀; “1.V.1915”, det. “*Anoplius viaticus* L., ♀” – 1♀; “19...”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Anoplius viaticus* L., ♀” – 1♀; “4.VII.1951, det. Zonstein, 1996 – *Anoplius viaticus* L.” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Genus *Pareiocurgus* Haupt, 1962

Pareiocurgus nomada (Kohl, 1889) (Kashkadarya Region: see Mokrousov and Zryanin 2015: 39).

Pareiocurgus nomada latigena (F. Morawitz, 1893) (Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya, Navoi, Tashkent Regions: see Zonstein 2000: 180; Wolf 2005: 1749; Kashkadarya Region: see Mokrousov and Zryanin 2015: 40).

Material: “UZBEKISTAN: Jizzakh Region: “Uzbekistan, ushh. Kumarishkent-saj, yu. skl. Turkestanskogo xr., 19.04.1961, Bekuzin”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Pareiocurgus latigenus* (F. Mor.)” – 1♀; Tashkent Region: “Karzhantau, zont. lugostep`, 28.IV.1940, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Pareiocurgus latigena* (F. Mor.)” – 2♀; “Tashkentskaya obl., xr. Karzhantau, zont. lugostep`, czvety` F. karatavica, 5.VI.1940, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det. – “*Pareiocurgus latigena* F. Mor.” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, suxie sklony`, Kshi dliurta, 7.VI.1940, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Pareiocurgus latigena* F. Mor.” – 1♀; vy`gorela - “19...”, det. “*Psammochares latigena*, ♀”; “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Pareiocurgus latigena* (F. Mor.)” – 1♀; “Iczov., 20.V.19...”, “M. Meyer det. – *Psammochares latigena* Mor.”; “Zonstein det. det., 1996 – *Psammochares latigena* Mor. N. Mur.” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Tribe Eidopompilini Arnold, 1936

Genus *Gonaporus* Ashmead, 1902

Subgenus *Gonaporus* Zonstein, 2001

Gonaporus (Gonaporus) ecbatonus, Wolf, 1990 (= *Gonaporus (Gonaporus) flamingo* Zonstein, 2001a) (Surkhandarya Region, Baisun: see Zonstein 2001b: 140; Fergana Valley: see Zonstein, Wahis 2015: 21).

Subgenus *Stigmaporus* Zonstein, 2001

Gonaporus (Stigmaporus) wolfi Zonstein, 2001 (Kyzylkum, Gazli: see Zonstein 2001b: 143).

Genus *Kentronaporus* Wolf, 1990

Kentronaporus pachionys Wolf, 1990 (Khorezm Region, Khiva: see Wolf 1990: 636).

Genus *Microphadnus* Cameron, 1905

Microphadnus griseus Zonstein, 2001 (Kashksdarya Region, Shakhrisabz: see Zonstein 2001b: 146).

Microphadnus pumilus (Costa, 1886) (Kashksdarya Region: Zonstein 2001b: 145; Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 173).

Genus *Tachyagetes* Haupt, 1930**Subgenus *Tachyagetes* Haupt, 1930**

Tachyagetes (*Tachyagetes*) *aegyptiacus* (Priesner, 1955) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 2005: 1750).

Tachyagetes (*Tachyagetes*) *aeratus* Priesner, 1955 (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 2005: 1750).

Tachyagetes (*Tachyagetes*) *argentatus* Haupt, 1930 (Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 174).

Tachyagetes (*Tachyagetes*) *aschabadus* Wolf, 1994 (Samarkand Region, Kumak: see Wolf 1994: 909).

Tachyagetes (*Tachyagetes*) *bactrianus* Zonstein, 2000 (Samarkand Region: see Zonstein 2000: 174).

Tachyagetes (*Tachyagetes*) *beersebus* Wolf, 1986 (Khorezm Region, Khiva: see Wolf 1994: 914).

Tachyagetes (*Tachyagetes*) *bytinskii* Haupt, 1962 (Samarkand Region, Kumak: see Wolf 1994: 914).

Tachyagetes (*Tachyagetes*) *excellens* Haupt, 1930.

Material: First record for UZBEKISTAN: “Xorezmskaya obl., Amu-dar`ya, predgor`ya Sultan-Uizdaga, Statia okolepis, 25.V.1941, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Tachyagetes* sp. aff. *excellens*” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Tachyagetes (*Tachyagetes*) *filicornis* (Tournier, 1889) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 2005: 1750; Lelej et al. 2017: 30; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 174).

Tachyagetes (Tachyagetes) grandis (Tournier, 1889) (= *Aporus (Aporus) ater* Radoszkowski, 1877) (Uzbekistan ("Kisilkum", "Sarafsch. dol.", "Keles", "Tschardara"): see Wolf 1987: 430).

Material: Jizzakh Region: "Pusty`nya, sev. Nuratinskix gor, 20.V".1925, "S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Tachyagetes grandis* Tournier, ♀" – 1♀; Fergana Valley: "Fergansk. dolina, st. Iessen, na gigantskom molochae, 15.IV.1940, Chirkun", "S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Tachyagetes grandis* Tourn." – 1♀; "Fergansk. dol., ksh. Laul`gan, ady`ry`, 30.IV.1940, Chirkun", "S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Tachyagetes grandis* Tournier, ♀" – 2♀ (GMPUz).

Tachyagetes (Tachyagetes) gratiosus (Radoszkowski, 1893) (= *Tachyagetes (Tachyagetes) kasakstanus* Wolf, 1987) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1987: 433; Samarkand, Tashkent Regions: see Zonstein 2000: 178; Tashkent Region: see Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002: 116; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170; Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 174).

Tachyagetes (Tachyagetes) kaspiscinus Wolf, 1994 (Samarkand Region, Kumak: see Wolf 1994: 910).

Tachyagetes (Tachyagetes) leucocnemis Haupt, 1930 (Tashkent Region, Chirchik: see Wolf 1998: 347).

Tachyagetes (Tachyagetes) maculipennis Zonstein, 2000 (Jizzakh, Tashkent, Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya Regions: see Zonstein 2000: 173).

Tachyagetes (Tachyagetes) otus Zonstein, 2000 (Fergana Valley, Tashkent Region: see Zonstein 2000: 173-174).

Tachyagetes (Tachyagetes) pseudiberomaculatus Wolf, 1994 (Khiva, Tashkent: see Wolf 1994: 912).

Tachyagetes (Tachyagetes) tsakaspus Wolf, 1994 (Fergana Region, Assake: see Wolf 1994: 913).

Subgenus *Epagetes* Priesner, 1955

Tachyagetes (Epagetes) testaceoides Wolf, 1982 (Bukhara, Surkhandarya Regions: see Zonstein 2000: 171-172).

Tachyagetes (Epagetes) testaceus (Radoszkowski, 1877) (Navoi Region: see Wolf 1982: 185; Navoi: see Zonstein 2000: 171).

Tachyagetes sp. (Surkhandarya Region: see Mokrousov and Zryanin 2015: 40).

Genus *Xenaporus* Ashmead, 1902**Subgenus *Baguenaia* Giner Mari, 1942**

Xenaporus (Baguenaia) vegteri (Wolf, 1981) (Buchara, Chiwa: see Wolf, 1990: 667; sands nr. Yazyavan, Central Ferghana: see Zonstein 2002a: 109).

Subgenus *Xenaporus* Ashmead, 1902

Xenaporus (Xenaporus) eremocanus Wolf, 1990 (Chiva: see Wolf 1990: 646; Zonstein 2002a: 106; Khorezm Region (Khiva), Fergana Region (Yazyavan): see Zonstein, Zonstein 2007: 269, 273; Loktionov and Lelej 2015; 2017: 174).

Xenaporus (Xenaporus) ignoteremus Wolf, 1990 (Uzbekistan: see Zonstein 2002a: 106).

Xenaporus (Xenaporus) karakumus Wolf, 1990 (Buchara: see Zonstein 2002a: 107).

Xenaporus (Xenaporus) krasnovodus Wolf, 1990 (Chiva: see Wolf 1990: 654).

Xenaporus (Xenaporus) krysanovskii Wolf, 1988 (Dzhira-Kuduk: see Zonstein 2002a: 107).

Xenaporus (Xenaporus) lomonossovi Wolf, 1990 (Karschi: see Wolf 1990: 656; Zonstein 2002a: 108).

Xenaporus (Xenaporus) serafschanus Wolf, 1990 (Chiva: see Wolf 1990: 663; Zonstein 2002a: 108).

Xenaporus (Xenaporus) tamerlan S. Zonstein, 2002 (Kashkadaria, near Shakhrisabz: see Zonstein 2002a: 108-109; Kashkadarya (Shakhrisabz): see Zonstein, Zonstein 2007: 269, 282).

Xenaporus (Xenaporus) vulpecula I. Zonstein & S. Zonstein, 2007 (Surkhandarya: see Zonstein, Zonstein 2007: 269, 284).

Tribe Episyronini Haupt, 1950**Genus *Episyron* Schiødte, 1837**

Episyron albonotatum (Vander Linden, 1827) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 341; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 166).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: Fergana Valley: “Fergansk. dol., k. Yaz-Yavan, peski, 8.V.1944, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Episyron* sp. aff. *albonotatum*” – 1♀; label discoloured, “2.VIII.47, Tip...”, det. “*Batazonus albonotatus* L.” – 1♀, outdated combination; label discoloured, “19...”, det. “*Batonus* sp.” – 1♀ (the genus definition is incorrect) (GMPUz).

Episyron candiotum Wahis, 1966 (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 341; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 167).

Episyron gallicum (Tournier, 1889) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 341; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 167).

Episyron rufipes (Linnaeus, 1758) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 341; 2005: 1748; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 167).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: Tashkent Region: “Ak-tash, 25.V.26, N. Kuznecov”, det. “*Episyron rufipes* L., ♂” – 1♂ (GMPUz).

Genus *Parabatozonus* Yasumatsu, 1936 (= *Batozonellus* Arnold, 1937)

Parabatozonus lacerticida (Pallas, 1771) (= *Batozonellus lacerticida* (Pallas, 1771)) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 337; 2005: 1746; Tashkent Region: see Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002: 116; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170; Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 167).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: Khorezm Region: “bereg Amu-dar`i, Sultanuizdag, 25.V.41, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Batozonellus lacerticida* Pall.” – 2♀, “Xorezmsk. obl., k. Xtaj i okrestnosti, 7.VI.41, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Batozonellus lacerticida* Pall.” – 1♀; “Xorezmsk. obl., k. Xtaj, 8.VI.41, Chirkun”, “N. Meyer det. – *Batasonus lacerticida* Pass.” – 1♀; Tashkent Region: “Karzhantau, zlakovozontich. step`, III poyasa, 29.VI.37”, det. “*Batasonus lacerticida* Pall., ♂” – 1♂; Ferghana Valley: “Severny`j Alaj, Shaximardan, 14.VIII.1937, Ady`lov”, “N. Meyer det. – *Batasonus lacerticida* Rass.”; “N. Meyer det. – *Batasonus lacerticida* Pall.” – 1♀; “Fergansk. dol., k. Ming-Bulak, S-dar`ya, Tamarisk, 11.V.1940, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Batozonellus lacerticida* Pall.” – 1♀; “1.V.1909, Xilkova”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Batozonellus lacerticida* Pall.” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Tribe Pompilini Latreille, 1805

Genus *Agenioideus* Ashmead, 1902 (= *Ridestus* Banks, 1912)

Subgenus *Agenioideus* Ashmead, 1902

Agenioideus (Agenioideus) sericeus (Vander Linden, 1827) (Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 167).

Subgenus *Schizanoplius* Cameron, 1904

Agenioideus (*Schizanoplius*) *ciliatus* (Lepeletier, 1845) (= *Ridestus* (*Schizanoplius*) *ciliatus* (Lepeletier, 1845)) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 332; 2005: 1742; Tashkent Region: see Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002: 116; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170; Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 167).

Agenioideus (*Schizanoplius*) *dichrous* (Brullé, 1840) (= *Ridestus* (*Schizanoplius*) *dichrous* (Brullé, 1840)) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 332; Tashkent Region: see Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002: 116; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170).

Agenioideus (*Schizanoplius*) *excisus* (F. Morawitz, 1890) (= *Ridestus* (*Schizanoplius*) *excisus* (F. Morawitz, 1890)) (Tashkent Region: see Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002: 116; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: “Chp. Micheuli, C.-D., 28.VI.11”, det. “*Psammochares excisus* F. Mor., ♀”; “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Agenioideus* (*Ridestus*) *excisus* F. Mor., ♀” – 1♀; “Amu-Dar`ya, Chugerum, zakr. pusty`nya, 19.VIII.1989”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Agenioideus* (*Ridestus*) *excisus* F. Mor., ♀” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Genus *Aporinellus* Banks, 1911**Subgenus *Aporinellus* Banks, 1911**

Aporinellus (*Aporinellus*) *moestus* (Klug, 1834) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 334; Tashkent Region: see Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002: 116; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170; Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 168).

Aporinellus (*Aporinellus*) *sexmaculatus* (Spinola, 1805) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 334; Tashkent Region: see Zonstein and Ovchinnikov 2002: 116; Vashetko and Chebotarev 2007: 170; Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 168).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: Fergana Valley: “Fergansk. dol., st. Iessen, na gigant-skom molochae, 19.V.1940, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Aporinellus sexmaculatus* sp.” – 2♀ (GMPUz).

Genus *Arachnospila* Kincaid, 1900**Subgenus *Ammosphex* Wilcke, 1942**

Arachnospila (*Ammosphex*) *consobrina* (Dahlbom, 1843) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 335; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 168-169; Shlyakhtenok et al. 2021: 278).

Arachnospila (Ammosphex) trivialis (Dahlbom, 1843).

Material: First record for UZBEKISTAN: Khorezm Region: “Xorezmsk. obl., k. Gazorat, ozero Shik, 15.V.41, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Arachnospila* sp. aff. *trivialis*” – 1♀; “Xorezmsk. obl., k. Xtaj, 8.VI.41, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Arachnospila* sp. aff. *trivialis*” – 1♀; Tashkent Region: “Karzhantau, kish. Dzhurt, sneg, 7.VI.1940, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Arachnospila* sp. aff. *trivialis*” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, kish. Dzhurt, suxie sklony`, 7.VI.1940, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Arachnospila* sp. aff. *trivialis*” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, zont. lugostep`, czvety` F. karatavica, 31.V.1940, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Arachnospila* sp. aff. *trivialis*” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, py`rejnaya lugostep`, 26.V.1940, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Arachnospila* sp. aff. *trivialis*., ♀” – 1♀; 1♀: “24.VI.19...”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Arachnospila* sp. aff. *trivialis*” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Arachnospila (Ammosphex) sp. 1 (Kashkadarya Region: see Mokrousov and Zryanin 2015: 39).

Arachnospila (Ammosphex) sp. 2 (Kashkadarya Region: see Mokrousov and Zryanin 2015: 39).

Subgenus *Anoplochaes* Banks, 1939

Arachnospila (Anoplochaes) fuscomarginata (Thomson, 1870) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 335; 2005: 1744; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 169; Shlyakhtenok et al. 2021: 278).

Arachnospila (Anoplochaes) spissa (Schiodte, 1837) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 335; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 170; Shlyakhtenok et al. 2021: 281).

Subgenus *Arachnospila* Kincaid, 1900

Arachnospila (Arachnospila) binaeva Haupt, 1930.

Material: First record for UZBEKISTAN: Tashkent Region: “Karzhantau, zlakovo-zontichnaya step`, 29.VI.37”, det. “*Psammochares binaevus* Hpt., ♀” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Arachnospila (Arachnospila) rufa (Haupt, 1927).

Material: First record for UZBEKISTAN: Tashkent Region: “Karzhantau, subal`pijskij lug, 3.VII.1939, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Arachnospila* sp. aff. *rufa*” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, Uluk-Dzhurt, 12.VIII.1939, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Arachnospila* sp. aff. *rufa*” – 1♀; “Karzhantau, zont. lugostep`, czvety` F. karatavica, 31.V.1940, Obuxova”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Arachnospila* sp. aff. *rufa*” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Arachnospila (Arachnospila) sogdianoides (Wolf, 1964) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 335; Loktionov and Lelej 2014: 272, 2017: 170).

Arachnospila (Arachnospila) vagans (Radoszkowski, 1877) (Samarkand Region (Aman-Kutan): see Zonstein 2002b: 115).

Genus *Dicyrtomellus* Gussakovskij, 1935

Dicyrtomellus kizilkumi (Radoszkowski, 1877) (Uzbekistan: see Radoszkovskij 1877b: 19; Navoi Region: see Davletshina et al. 1979: 117).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: Khorezm Region: “Xiva, okrestnosti, peski, 4.V.41, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Dicyrtomellus kizilkumi* Rad.” – 2♀; “Xivinsk. oasis, peski u oz. Kori, 28.IV.41, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Dicyrtomellus kizilkumi* Rad., ♂” – 1♂; “Xivinskij oasis, k. Dashak, peski, 30.IV.41, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Dicyrtomellus kizilkumi* Rad.” – 2♀; “bereg Amudar`i, Sultan-uiz-dag, 25.V.41, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Dicyrtomellus* sp.” – 2♀, 1♂; Navoi Region: “Yu. Kizil Kumy`, k S. ot Nurat. xr., 22.V.26, E`ksp”, det. “*Dicyrtomellus kizilkumi* Rad., ♀” – 1♀; “Tamdy`, Kzy`l Kum, bokchi, 12.VI.37, A.”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Dicyrtomellus kizilkumi* F. Mor., ♀” – 1♀; “okr. pos. Kara-Kul`, pusty`nya Ky`zy`l-Kum, SZ-Uzbekistan, 16 V 1978, G.F. Kolyux”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Dicyrtomellus kizilkumi* (F. Mor.)” – 1♀; “YuV Ky`zy`lkum, Uzb., ur. Murun-Karak, okr. Kamy`sh-Bulaka, 16 V 1965, G.F. Kolyux”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Dicyrtomellus kizilkumi* (F. Mor.), ♀” – 3♀; Bukhara Region: “okr. Gazli, Ky`zy`l-Kum, 19.05.1960, Bekuzin”, “S. Zonstein det., 1997 – *Dicyrtomellus kizilkumi* (F. Mor.), ♀” – 1♀; Jizzakh Region: “Pusty`nya sev. Nuratinskix gor, Mangly`kly`k, 29.V.26”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Dicyrtomellus kizilkumi* F. Mor., ♂” – 1♂ (GMPUz).

Dicyrtomellus pseudokyzylkumi Wolf, 1988 (the valley of Zarafshan River: see Wolf 1988a: 223).

Dicyrtomellus tingitanus (Wolf, 1966) (Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 170).

Genus *Evagetes* Lepeletier, 1845

Evagetes pectinipes (Linnaeus, 1758) (Uzbekistan: see Loktionov and Lelej 2009: 391, 2014: 286, 2017: 171; Loktionov 2011: 210; Lelej and Loktionov 2012: 410).

Evagetes siculus contemptus (Tournier, 1890) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 2005: 1749; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 171 (as *E. siculus*)).

Genus *Nanoclavelia* Haupt, 1962

Nanoclavelia leucoptera (Dahlbom, 1845) (Tashkent Region: see Wolf 1998: 343).

Genus *Pamirospila* Wolf, 1970

Pamirospila hetaera Zonstein, 2000 (Tashkent Region: see Zonstein 2000: 183).

Genus *Paracyphononyx* Gribodo, 1884

Paracyphononyx pavlovskyi Gussakovskij, 1952.

Material: First record for UZBEKISTAN: Khorezm Region: “Xivinsk. oasis, k. Dashak, peski, 30.IV.41, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Paracyphononyx pavlovskyi* Guss., ♂” – 1♂; “Bereg Amu-dar`i, Sultan-Uizdag, 25.V.41, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Paracyphononyx pavlovskyi* Guss., ♂” – 1♂ (GMPUz).

Genus *Schistonyx* Saussure, 1887

Schistonyx antrax (Dalla Torre, 1897) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 346 – = *Pompilus anthracinus* Taschenberg, 1880; = *Schistonyx anthracinus* (F. Morawitz, 1890); junior synonym – *Schistonyx anthrax* (Dalla Torre, 1897).

Material: Khorezm Region: “Bereg Amu-Dar`i, Sultanuizdag, 25.V.41, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Schistonyx antrax* D.T., ♀” – 1♀; “Xorezmsk. obl., trava u oz. Shik, 15.V.41, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Schistonyx* sp.” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Genus *Telostegus* Costa, 1887

Telostegus montanus (Zonstein, 2001) (Uzbekistan: see Zonstein 2001b: 147 – = *Elaphrosyrion montanum* Zonstein, 2001).

Telostegus sabulicola Priesner, 1955 (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 2005: 1752).

Telostegus zonsteini (Wolf, 2001) (Samarkand Region: see Wolf 2001: 971).

Telostegus sp.

Material: UZBEKISTAN: Khorezm Region: “Xorezmsk. obl., Dzhumurtau, 21.V.41, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Telostegus* sp.” – 2♀; “Xorezmsk. obl., Sultan-Uizdag, 29.V.41, Chirkun”, “S. Zonstein det., 1996 – *Telostegus* sp., ♀” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Tribe Psammoderini Arnold, 1937**Genus *Arachnotheutes* Haupt, 1927**

Arachnotheutes rufithorax (Costa, 1882).

Material: First record for UZBEKISTAN: Khorezm Region: “Xorezmsk. obl., Dzhumurtau, 21.V.41, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Arachnotheutes rufithorax* Costa, ♂” – 1♂ (GMPUz).

Genus *Eoferreola* Arnold, 1935

Eoferreola distincta (Smith, 1855) (Uzbekistan: see Wahis and Schmid-Egger 2002: 49-52).

Eoferreola manticata (Pallas, 1771) (junior synonym *Eoferreola caucasica* (Radoszkowski, 1888) (Uzbekistan: see Wahis and Schmid-Egger 2002: 56; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 173).

Material: UZBEKISTAN: Fergana Valley: “Fergansk. dol., st. Iessen, ady`ry`, 19.V.1940, Chirkun”, “Zonstein det., 1996 – *Eoferreola caucasica* Rad., ♀” – 1♀ (GMPUz).

Eoferreola manticata f. *batrachiorum* (Dalla Torre) (Uzbekistan: see Wahis and Schmid-Egger 2002: 62).

Eoferreola nigra (Radoszkowski); Wolf, 1998 (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 341; Wahis and Schmid-Egger 2002: 56).

Eoferreola rhombica (Christ, 1791) (Uzbekistan: see Wolf 1998: 341; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 173).

Eoferreola variabilis (Eversmann, 1849) (= *Pompilus variabilis* Eversmann, 1849) (Uzbekistan: see Lelej et al. 2017: 29; Loktionov and Lelej 2017: 173).

Genus *Ferreola* Lapeletier, 1845

Ferreola heladai Schmidt-Egger and Al-Djahdami, 2018 (Fergana Region (Kokand): see Schmidt-Egger and Al-Djahdami 2018: 402).

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of literature on spider wasps (Pompilidae) and the study of specimens from the entomological collection of the State Museum of Nature of Uz-

Uzbekistan, the taxonomic composition of the spider wasps of Uzbekistan has been determined. It includes 132 species, 1 subspecies, and 4 species (sp.) belonging to 23 subgenera, 28 genera, 8 tribes, and 3 subfamilies. Among them, 9 species are recorded for the first time in the fauna of Uzbekistan: *Cryptocheilus (Cryptocheilus) alternatus caspius* Gussakovskij, 1952; *Priocnemis (Priocnemis) minuta* (Vander Linden, 1827); *Priocnemis (Umbripennis) gypsochtona* Gussakovskij, 1930; *Tachyagetes (Tachyagetes) excellens* (Haupt, 1930); *Arachnospila (Ammosphex) trivialis* (Dahlbom, 1843); *Arachnospila (Arachnospila) binaeva* Haupt, 1930; *Arachnospila (Arachnospila) rufa* (Haupt, 1927); *Paracyphononyx pavlovskyi* Gussakovskij, 1952; *Schistonyx antrax* (Dalla Torre, 1897); *Arachnotheutes rufithorax* (Costa, 1882); *Eoferreola caucasica* (Radoszkowski, 1888).

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